

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14246723

Vol. 07 Issue 10 Oct - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01465

Prioritizing Training Needs of Disadvantaged Young Women for Improved Livelihood in Delta State, Nigeria

ANHO, Roseline Okiemute¹

OBATA, Rita Obiageli²

BIOKORO, 'Ogharen Beauty³

¹²³Department of Educational Management and Foundations, Delta State University, Abraka

Abstract

The paper examines prioritizing training needs of disadvantages young women for improved livelihood in Delta State. The investigation made use of secondary data in reviewing training needs and its impact on disadvantage young women in the state. The study revealed in its findings that prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women empowers them to contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the society. Also, the study found that the training of young women built in them self confidence and self-esteem in their desires to actualize their dream and aspirations. The paper concludes that training embarked for young women in the state has the capacity to develop and empower them to contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the state. Also, the study discovered that, prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women ensures that they liberated from the male counterpart and cultural factors and empowered economically for improved livelihood for personal and societal development. The paper recommends that government agencies charged with the welfare of women should organize regular, that is quarterly training on various skills in a bit to empower young women in the state, special orientation exercise by orientation agency should be carried out across the state to sensitize residents on the imperative of empowering women for family and societal growth and development.

Keywords: Training Need, Young Women, Education, Empowerment.

How to cite: Roseline Okiemute, A., Rita Obiageli, O., & 'Ogharen Beauty, B. (2024). Prioritizing Training Needs of Disadvantaged Young Women for Improved Livelihood in Delta State, Nigeria. *GPH-International Journal of Educational Research*, 7(10), 88-97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246723>

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

Introduction

Training is education and knowledge acquired to undertake a task. Education in the 21st century has gone beyond just the mere formal training of the individual in an educational institution. This is because education now is geared towards inculcating in the individual the skills needed to face societal and environmental challenges be it in the form of social, political, economic, etc that is prevalent in the society cum Delta State. Education is geared towards empowering the individual, as in this case, the disadvantaged young women so that they will be better placed to face challenges occurring on a daily basis and impediment that they face as a result of their sex. The female sex is being view as a weaker sex because of mainly societal/traditional variables that to a large extent is disadvantageous to the female sex. This disadvantaged position faced by the female sex necessitated the need for training to improve their livelihood in a society that is dominated by the male sex.

Training needs for the disadvantaged young women is geared at empowering them both mentally and physically so that they will be able to tackle and face obstacles placed in their part of progress inadvertently by society. The imperative of training of the disadvantaged young women in Delta State cannot be overemphasized. It is a springboard that will elevate their lots in the male-dominated society and improve their tendency to be self-reliant and independent from the male sex as this will ensure that they are not under the apron of the male in the scheme of things in the state. Training is the action of teaching a person a particular skill of behaviour. In this context, the training of disadvantaged young women will make them acquire skills that will be pivotal to their livelihood and enhance their capacity to be self -dependent and confident in their daily dealings in the society where they live. Training entails a situation whereby a person acquire a skill that become useful overtime in the course of undertaking a task that involves the adoption and application of literacy and knowledge in accomplishing the said task. According to the Business Dictionary (2019), training is an organized activity aimed at imparting information and/or instructions to improve the recipients' performance or to help him or her attain a required level of knowledge or skill. Impact from this definition is that training of the disadvantaged young women will ensure that they are made independent via the provision of adequate skills and knowledge required to live and survive in an environment that is gender sensitive to virtually all things and issues. Prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women in Delta State cannot be over emphasized. It is a means by which women who live in a culturally and traditionally inclined society like Delta State are empowered to be independent and confident, giving credence to the fact that, a woman self-reliance is what will make her achieve improved livelihood. Thus, training needs giving to women for the sake of improved livelihood cannot be overstressed. It ensures that women and cordoned off vices like prostitution, begging, hawking, amongst others, inimical to their well-being and development.

The training of disadvantaged young women comes in the form of formal education or the adoption of vocational training via empowerment that provide arsenal for women to face challenges and weather the storm shadowing their growth and development. In this light, education and vocational training should be prioritized, implemented and monitored by the

state government to ensure that its noble aim and objectives are achieved within stipulated framework.

The training needs of disadvantaged young women in the state ensure that women are empowered to cater for their well-being as against their over dependence on the male sex and others for sustenance. This notion was given impetus by the Develop Africa Incorporated (2018) where it stated that, “training empowers economically disadvantaged women with little or no education; and that microfinance and technical support helps women to regain economic independence, value and self-esteem”. The imperative here is that, the training of women, especially the disadvantaged once, will ensure that, they are provided with arsenal to tackle challenges posed by societal factors that encourages discrimination against young women. Thus, the imperative of identifying the training needs to disadvantaged women cannot be overemphasized. In the view of the Wikipedia (2019), training needs of disadvantaged young women is the process of identifying the gap between what they have and possess and what they need in order to survive and live successfully and independently in the society in which they live; and in this sense, there is need for an analysis to be undertaken to determine the imperative of their needs that will to a large extent empower them to be independent of their male counterpart and also empower them adequately so that they will effectively contribute to the growth and development of their society; as empowering a woman is synonymous with empowering the nation. The identification of these needs and in whatever form is the first stage in the training process in improving the lots of the disadvantaged young women and it involves a series of steps that reveals whether training will help to solve observable and inherent problems which has been identified. Training can be described as “the acquisition of skills, concepts or attitudes that results in improved performance and well-being within the environment”. Implicit here is the fact that training of the disadvantaged young women in the society will go a long way in making them independent, improves their livelihood, reduces risks and temptations associated with lack and empower them to contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the nation. It is noteworthy to state here that, before training is undertaken for the for the benefit of the disadvantaged young women, there is need to conduct a training needs analysis to determine the type and extent of needs that is needed to effectively empower young women who are disadvantaged in the society under investigation. Training Needs Analysis (TNA) entails a situation of identifying the gap between disadvantaged young women training and needs of training. Training needs analysis is most often used as part of the system development process that helps the individuals, organizations and government responsible for the training to derive its anticipated benefits of self-reliance, organizational improvement and profitability and state growth and development. Due to the close tie between the design of the system and the training required, in most cases it runs alongside the development to capture the training requirements so that beneficiary can efficiently maximize the tenets of the training in building their individual dream, goals and aspiration of self-reliant and independence.

Many disadvantaged women in Nigeria generally and Delta State in particular does not have access to the training and resources that will help them become independent and financially sufficient. Due to little or no education, they are powerless and locked in a vicious

cycle that keeps unraveling the difficulty of life and living in their faces. In line with this notion and perception, training, whether educational or otherwise of women becomes necessary as it will empower them to undertake task independently. According to United State Navy, Center for Personal Professional Development (2010) as cited by Lawrence and Egbule (2021), training is teaching or developing in oneself or others, any [skills](#) and [knowledge](#) that relate to specific [useful competencies](#). They stated further that, training has specific goals of improving one's [capability](#), capacity, [productivity](#) and [performance](#); as it forms the core of [apprenticeships](#) and provides the backbone of content at [institutes of technology](#) (also known as technical colleges or polytechnics). In addition to the basic training required for a [trade, occupation](#) or [profession](#), observers of the labour-market recognize as of 2008 the need to continue training beyond initial qualifications; to maintain, upgrade and update skills throughout [working life](#). People within many professions and occupations may refer to this sort of training as [professional development](#). Implicit here is the fact that training of women should be a continuous one due to the vital role women play in the society. As observed by Aguinis, Herman, Kraiger, Kurt (2009), training a woman ensure and secure the family and by extension the home. This observation by Aguinis et al emphasized the vital nature that the training, development and empowering of young women takes in a society, especially in a more traditional society like Delta State with its culture that are pro-men and anti-women. They see training and development as a means of improving the effectiveness of the individuals in undertaking tasks. The training needs of disadvantaged young women for improved livelihood cannot be overemphasized; hence this study investigated the imperative prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women for improved livelihood in the state will have in the growth and development of the state moving forward.

The need to train women, especially the disadvantaged once cannot be overstressed in this clime. It is a basis upon which young women under investigation are empowered to be independent and self-reliant. The over dependence of young women on their male sex is a cause for concern as it has led to various problems as the male sex very often wants to take advantage of their position in the life of the young women to dominate them, hence such dominance do lead to a myriad of vices inimical to the growth and development of the women. This vulnerability of the young women has necessitated the imperative for training needs for these women to improve their livelihood and independence. Against this backdrop, this paper investigates prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women and improved livelihood in Delta State. To effectively carry out this investigation, the paper was guided by the following objective

Objective of the Study

- To find out the extent prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women will improve their livelihood in Delta State, Nigeria

Concept of Training and Disadvantaged Young Women

Training entails the acquisition of skills for the performance of a task. It empowers an individual to undertake various noble task in a bit to improve livelihood. Training of an individual ensures that the individual is poised to contribute to the growth and development of the locality where he or she is based. This is because, when an individual is trained, skill is acquired and such skills is applied in the running and operating of a business which by extension leads to the development of the locality where the business is cited, provide means of livelihood for the trainee and assist in the alleviating of poverty and making the young women involved to be independent, self-reliant and industrious. Training for a job helps to build in confidence in undertaking task which by extension ensures that women involved are more capable and well equipped to face challenges inherent in Delta State and in particular societies in which they live and operate (UN Women, 2019).

Training entails the set of systematic events, as it is an organized activity for growing the skills of people for a definite purpose. Many authors define the term training in different manners. In the view of Pattanayak (2005), training is a planned programme designed to improve performance and to bring about measurable changes in knowledge, skills, attitude, and social behavior of employees doing a particular job. Implicit here is that fact that training of young women in Delta State will ensure that there present victimized and oppressed state is changed as a result of them undergoing a systematic training organized by individual, organizations or the state government with a bit to empowering them to face societal changes. Steinmez and Patten (2009) sees training as a short-term process utilizing a systematic and organized procedure by which non-managerial personnel learn technical knowledge and skill. In this light, the training of disadvantaged young women in the state will ensure that they are equipped with technical know-how and given skills that will assist them in undertaking task. This is because, as a young women, it is only a technically and knowledgeable women customers will patronize based on their gender inclination. Furthermore, Vasu(2002) opined that, training is an art of increasing the knowledge and skill of an employee for doing a particular job that he or she has been trained to do. The implication here is that young women will be trained based on their choice of skill they which to acquire and made to professionalize base on their chosen field; as this will help in galvanizing their patronage within and outside the society. However, Saxena (2000) is of the opinion that training is any organizationally planned effort to change the behavior or attitudes of employees so that they can perform jobs on acceptable standards. Noting that, it provides knowledge and skills required to perform the job. The notion of Saxenawas given credence by Obaro (2017) entailing that training given to young women will enable them to undertake task and job in the highest standard and quality as the job requires. Also, this view shows that when women are trained, they are more qualified and effective in undertaking task with quality at the back of their minds. Pattanayak, Nair and Nair (2004) described training as a short term learning process, which is 'application specific' and limited for a specific job requirements instead of improving skill or knowledge, which has immediate application to the benefit of the individual as well as the organization. Their view of training conceptualizes it as a short term thing that is aimed at achieving a specific target. The implication here is that more young

women are trained when there is time specific, like say, every 3month, being set aside to actualize a given objective. Thus, the adoption of this notion by Pattanayak et al will ensure that more disadvantaged young women are catered for in more areas within the state.

Training Needs for Disadvantaged Young Women

A training need is a gap between the knowledge, skills and attitudes desired and already possessed by the employees. These three are attributes of a successful training that helps the disadvantage young women to bridge the divide existing between the way young women are perceived and what they can actually achieve. These perceptions also ensures that women can adequately contribute to the growth and development of the state. Training becomes imperative when disadvantaged young women performance, ability, behaviour, etc falls short of standards and expectations, i.e. when there is performance is at variance with expectation. Inadequacy in performance/ability may be due to lack of skill or knowledge or any other problems like cultural factors or gender stereotyping within or outside the individual's society. The problem of deficiency, lack of contribution to societal growth and development by the disadvantaged young women can be remedied by a proper training undertaken by stakeholders in the communities in particular and state in general. The implication here is that when proper, needed and adequate training are given to young women, they develop sound virtues and attributes that will propel them towards actualizing individual dreams and goals and contributing to the growth and development of their personal family and state in general (Jacoby, 2004; Egbule&Egbule, 2008).

Most Nigeria, Deltans inclusive still operates in a traditional setting whereby they believe that the role of the woman is purely domestic and as such, they are not considered for any form of training that do not take cognizance of their traditional role (domestic) into consideration. Hence, young women in this clime are consigned to domestic affair notwithstanding their potential to societal growth and development via the acquisition of skills, either formal or non-formal as the case may be. They are being denied access to the three domain of knowledge that would have served to better their lots in their zeal to contribute their quota to society by means of assisting in growth, development and knowledge acquisition. These bottlenecks to young women acquisition of knowledge via training is manifesting in diverse form which by extension is preventing and hampering them from actualizing their dream. These hindrances includes but not limited to:

Training/Financial Capital: Young women lack access to financial capital for developmental purposes and have limited opportunities to gain education, knowledge, and skills that can lead to economic advancement without the direct involvement of guardian or stakeholder in the environment.

Lack of Adequate Women-Friendly Policy: Inadequate policy frameworks and inequitable gender norms with regards to young women also often create barriers to their economic, social and political advancement.

In the light of the above observations, the Adolescent Girls' Advocacy and Leadership Initiative (AGALI) (2013) as cited in Dunning (2017) noted that the Public Health Institute recently launched a global research report analyzing young women's economic empowerment strategies and made recommendations for policymakers, founders and practitioners. AGALI explores the factors that contribute and inhibit young women economic empowerment, growth and development and examines some approaches – financial, policy, employment, and life-skills and social support strategies that can be explored to solve the problem of young women being disadvantaged in the society.

For a sound financial strategy, it is important to link workforce development and employment strategies with market needs and opportunities. AGALI as cited by Obaro (2013) opined that programmes offering vocational training and employment opportunities should include these initiatives to match market requirements and opportunities. This approach not only requires designing a quality training process that builds young women's technical and soft skills, but also enlists the commitment of employers to hire participants. This aspect of the approach aims at empowering women via the provision of soft loans for business venture that will in the long run empower them to be self-reliant in the society.

Workforce development and employment strategies are critical to helping disadvantaged young women lift themselves and their families out of poverty. Although young women primarily enter the workforce to support their families financially, studies have shown that they also value mobility, opportunities for friendship, and greater autonomy that may come with employment. Therefore, safe and appropriate employment opportunities can strengthen their economic status, while improving social welfare and future job prospects.

Despite the clear benefits of investing in employment opportunities for young women, the global economic crisis has created serious challenges for youth employment. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2012)'s report, the global youth unemployment rate has risen since 2007 and medium-term projections suggest little improvement in the next few years. Further, macroeconomic conditions create particular young women who experience greater rates of unemployment compared to men in nearly every region of the world. Given these challenges, vocational and technical training for young women can play a key role in helping them get jobs and be self-sufficient. Vocational and technical training typically includes development of capacity, entrepreneurship and business skills. Ideally, vocational and technical training is interest-oriented and builds specific skills tailored to prospective individual's needs. These individual needs differs depending on the area of interest so chosen and stakeholders involved in the training being able to provide the requisite skills.

Conclusion

The study explore the benefit in prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women and improved livelihood in Delta State. The study concludes that training embarked for young women in the state has the capacity to develop and empower them to contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the state. Also, the study discovered that, prioritizing training needs of disadvantaged young women ensures that they liberated from the male counterpart and cultural factors and empowered economically for improved livelihood for personal and societal development.

Suggestion

Arising from the conclusion, the paper suggests that:

- Government agencies charged with the welfare of women should organize regular, that is quarterly training on various skills in a bit to empower young women in the state
- Special orientation exercise by orientation agency should be carried out across the state to sensitize residents on the imperative of empowering women for family and societal growth and development.

REFERENCES

- Aguinis, Herman; Kraiger, Kurt (January 2009). "[Benefits of Training and Development for Individuals and Teams, Organizations, and Society](#)". *Annual Review of Psychology*. 60 (1), 451–474.
- Business Dictionary (2019). Training. Retrieved 29th March, 2019 from www.businessdictionary.com/definition.
- Develop Africa Incorporated (2018). Training requirements. Retrieved 28th March, 2019 from www.ehow.com/training
- Dunning, D. (2017) Vocational training for young women: what works and what doesn't. Retrieved 28th March, 2019 from www.theguardian.com
- Egbule, J. F & Egbule, E. O. (2008). Clinical counselling: A psychotherapeutic approach. Real Choice Concept.
- International Labour Organization (ILO) (2012). Youth unemployment compared to manual of 1986. Retrieved 29th March, 2019 from www.ilo.org.
- Jacoby, J. (2004). "Making the case for parochial schools". The Boston Globe.
- Lawrence, K. C. & Egbule, E. O. (2021). Can emotional intelligence training cause a cease in tobacco smoking among school going adolescents? *International Journal of Adolescent and Youth*, 26(1), 356-366
- Pattanayak, B. (2005). Human resource management. 3rd edition. PHI, New Delhi.
- Pattanayak, B., Nair, N. G. & Nair, L. (2004). Personnel management and industrial relation. S. Chand & Co, New Delhi.
- Obaro, G. O. (2013). Library education and national development beyond 20:20. *Knowledge Review*, 33(20), 22-30
- Obaro, G. O. (2017). Availability and utilization of library information services by researchers in the social sciences in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria. *Information Technology*, 14(1)
- Saxena, J. P. & Anita, K. (2000). Training and development. Nice Printing Press. New Delhi.
- Steinmez, L. L. & Patten, R. J. (2009). Enthusiasm, interest and learning. The result of game training. *Training and Development Journal*, 21(4), 26-36.

Roseline Okiemute, A., Rita Obiageli, O., & 'Ogharen Beauty, B. (2024). Prioritizing Training Needs of Disadvantaged Young Women for Improved Livelihood in Delta State, Nigeria. *GPH-International Journal of Educational Research*, 7(10), 88-97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246723>

UNwomen (2019). Training for gender equality and women's empowerment. Retrieved 28th March, 2019 from www.unwomen.org

US Navy, Center for Personal Professional Development (2010). Navy Instructional Theory NAVEDTRA 14300A, Chapter 9 Course Materials. Retrieved 29th March, 2019.

Vasu, D. (2002). Training and development. Nice Printing Press, New Delhi.

Wikipedia (2019). Training. Retrieved 27th March, 2019 from www.wikipedia.org